

Fitting source geometry and Plume geometry

Source geometry	R ² value (Overestimated)				A			B			Pconv (a)				Pconv(b)					
	5	10	15	20	10	15	20	10	15	20	5	10	15	20	5	10	15	20		
Ms = 1m	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	2.69	2.90	2.82	1.10	1.18	1.15	0.02	0.02			0.02	0.02				
2 m	0.99	0.98	0.98	0.98	2.70	2.76	2.81	1.28	1.36	1.41	0.04		0.05		0.03		0.04			Fixed Small Ms
3	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	2.56	2.59	2.60	1.44	1.52	1.58	0.05			0.08	0.03			0.05	a	2.17-2.9
4	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	2.41	2.40	2.39	1.55	1.64	1.71	0.07		0.09		0.04		0.05		b	1.1-1.82
5	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	2.24	2.20	2.17	1.65	1.75	1.82	0.08	0.09			0.04	0.05				
Ws = 1m	0.76	0.70	0.67	0.64	2.17	2.88	2.92	0.29	0.23	0.19	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.03		
2	0.87	0.81	0.78	0.75	3.16	3.33	3.42	0.58	0.47	0.41	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.05		Fixed small Ws
3	0.87	0.87	0.85	0.82	3.19	3.40	3.54	0.79	0.68	0.60	0.10	0.1	0.09	0.09	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	a	2.17-3.53
4	0.91	0.91	0.89	0.87	3.13	3.38	3.53	0.96	0.84	0.76	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	b	0.19-1.09
5	0.94	0.94	0.92	0.90	3.03	3.30	3.48	1.09	0.97	0.89	0.10	0.10	0.06	0.11	0.06	0.06	0.11	0.06		

Source geometry	R ² value (Underestimated)		
	10	15	20
Ms = 1m	0.89	0.90	0.90
2 m	0.92	0.92	0.92
3	0.93	0.93	0.93
4	0.93	0.94	0.94
5	0.94	0.94	0.94
Ws = 1m	0.17	0.65	-1.24
2	0.56	0.42	0.31
3	0.73	0.67	0.60
4	0.82	0.76	0.72
5	0.82	0.82	0.78

Part of this work was completed in MSc. thesis work of Mr. Pawan Kumar Sapkota (HTW) under supervision of Dr. P. K. Yadav (TUD), Prof. R. Liedl (TUD) and Prof. T. Grieschek (HTW)